

HORIZON 2020

Research and Innovation action

Grant Agreement No. 730965

ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:

**A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic**

Deliverable 3.5

FrostBytes Videos from the Summer School participants

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	Educating a new generation of polar researchers and professionals
Deliverable no. & title	3.5 FrostBytes Videos from the Summer School participants
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Last change	
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1. Abstract

In the frame of ARICE Task 3.2, APECS is organizing the MOSAiC School, an in person/on-site training for 20 MSc. and PhD students from 11 countries. All students have created “FrostBytes” uploaded on vimeo on 6 August 2019.

Frostbytes are 30-60 minute short video recordings designed to help researchers easily share their latest findings to a broad audience. In case of the MOSAiC School participants who have a diverse background of natural sciences covering the MOSAiC themes of atmosphere, sea ice, ocean, ecosystem and biogeochemistry, the FrostBytes are aiming at an understanding of each other research interests. As science communication is a crucial part of the MOSAiC School, participants have also succeeded a first exercise, which will be evaluated onboard together with documentary producer and media representatives. Further on, lecturers get to know their audience beforehand and have a chance to better prepare their scientific lectures onboard. Lastly, the FrostBytes are an open online source for information on polar research and current science topics. Deliverable 3.5 therefor serves multiple audiences.

FrostByte titles

Author	FrostByte title	Individual link
Neil Aellen	Impact of turbulent surface on Arctic mixed-phase clouds	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352250472
Marylou Athanase	Atlantic water in the Eurasian Arctic Basin	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352248214
Sam Cornish	Arctic Ocean`s memory of atmosphere variability	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352253177
Francecsa Doglioni	Long term variability of Arctic Ocean surface circulation inferred from remote sensing and in situ observations	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352231610
Lisa Crow	Ice Lasagne: Understanding an ice shelf one layer at a time	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352234156
Anika Happe	Modelling of Habitat Quality with InVest Case Study, Ecuador	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352229722
Carolynn Harris	Microbial decomposition of organic matter in Antarctic Lakes	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352230229
Mauro Hermann	About the mass balance of S Greenland Glacier "Sermilik" and (thermos-)dynamical drivers of Greenland warm events	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352248674
Sean Horvath	Understanding the Variability and Predictability of Arctic Sea Ice Attributes	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352229280
Ewa Korejwo	The importance of natural and anthropogenic sources of mercury in polar ecosystems	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352230633

Robbie Mallett	Snow cover and sea ice thickness	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/355066859
Tatiana Matveeva	Reconstruction of Arctic sea ice at the first half on the 20th century	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352253774
Alex Mavrovic	Remote sensing of northern environments	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352872615
Rosalie McKay	Experimental and modelling study of subsea releases of oil	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352252116
Ryleigh Moore	The evolution of melt pond geometry	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352252689
Pierre Priou	Borealization of the Arctic pelagic ecosystem	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352251165
Natalia Ribeiro Santos	Meltwater reaching Vincennes Bay Polynya: What are the implications for Antarctic bottom water production	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352249483
Thea Schneider	The impact of improved turbulence parametrization for polar conditions in a regional Arctic climate model	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352255078
Igor Vasilevich	Current state of Arctic estuaries and methodological approach to its assessment	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352232506
Julika Zinke	Balloon-borne sampling of cloud water and chemical analysis of samples obtained in the High Arctic	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204/video/352232867

Dissemination

All FrostBytes are permanently and freely available on vimeo and added as a legacy to the APECS and ARICE, as well as to the MOSAiC homepage.

Links

Vimeo: <https://vimeo.com/showcase/6206204>

ARICE: <https://arice.eu/training/mosaic-school-2019/frostbyte-videos>

APECS: <https://www.apecs.is/events/upcoming-event-highlights/mosaic-school-2019.html>

MOSAiC: implementation planned

Promotion of the FrostBytes is planned via the APECS and ARICE social media channels twitter and facebook starting mid of September until end of October 2019 when the MOSAiC School is ending. Further promotion is expected when the participants will serve as MOSAiC Ambassadors with their created outreach projects during the full year of the MOSAiC expedition.